

From Self-Compassion to Enhanced Employees' Performance: Unveiling the Mediating Mechanism of Positive Psychological Functioning

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Abstract: *The objective of this research was to examine the mediating role of positive psychological functioning in the relationship between self-compassion and employees' performance. This research is supported with three theories: Self controlled theory as performance model, Self determination theory that focused on resources and Positive psychology/PERMA Model to develop link performance and engagement model. The sample consisted of 382 faculty members of the public and private sector, educational institutions (teaching faculty of universities) from Pakistan. Quantitative research design and deductive approach is applied to conduct the research. Results demonstrated a positive and significant relationship between self-compassion and employees' performance. The results also revealed that positive psychological functioning partially mediates the association between self-compassion and employees' performance. The results pointed out the significance of self-compassion in promoting employees' job performance in the presence of positive psychological functioning as a mediator. Research limitations and implications of the study are discussed in the end.*

Keywords: self-compassion, employees' performance, psychological functioning, mediation analysis

Introduction

Organizations are comprised of humans, and human pain in an organization is inevitable (Choudhary, Ismail & Hanif, 2017). Though self-compassion provides strength and resiliency in a time of pain as being supportive, kind, and being caring toward own self. Self-compassion is defined by Neff (2003) as "a self-attitude that involves treating oneself with warmth and understanding in difficult times and recognizing that making mistakes is a part of being human" (pp. 225). The literature of this field showed that self-compassion is important to the context of every profession (e.g. lawyers, nurses, administrators, counselors, doctors, police officers, and other services), particularly for teachers (Betoret & Artiga, 2010; Buchanan, 2010), as teaching is one of the most challenging jobs (Johnson et al., 2005) in which people expect more from teachers than a boss in an office or an employee in an organizational setting.

Self-compassion is a dynamic and vital concept of organizational psychology (Atkins & Parker, 2012), and linked with individuals or groups, in time of failure, deficiency, disappointment, inadequacy, and general situations (Neff, 2003). The author also stated that self-compassion is an essential strategy to deal with negative feelings (depression and negative emotions) and create optimistic approaches of thoughtfulness and social connections. Most recent definition of self-compassion presented by Gupta and Singh (2017) involves being encouraged and motivated and offering kindness, patience, and open-minded understanding, identifying that no one is perfect, and can make errors.

Moreover, self-compassion is a new research area (Choudhary et al., 2017), many investigations have been led with this new concept of “self-compassion” in recent decades (Neff, 2014). Neff (2009) identified six dimensions of self-compassion (negative and positive) and combined it into three components (mindfulness, self-kindness, awareness of common humanity,). The scholars conceptualize each having two parts known as: “kindness versus indifference/ self-judgment, mindfulness versus disengagement/ over-identification and common humanity versus separation/ isolation” (cited by; Barnard & Curry, 2011). These components occupied collective prime active features of self-compassion, letting people make an effort to improve and modify their behaviors and encourage their self-psychological comforts (Neff, 2011).

It is also evident from past researches that self-compassion is considered an essential factor to enhance employees’ performance (Innstrand et al., 2011). The review of previous studies shows that the association between self-compassion and employees’ outcome variables have been tested directly, or indirectly in clinical studies (Neff, Kirkpatrick & Rude, 2007; Gilbert, 2005), but there is a lack of consensus on a common understanding of the self-compassion in an organizational setting, specifically, in higher education institutions. Furthermore, the influence of self-compassion on employees’ performance with the mediating effect of psychological functioning remains unobserved. So, this research study tried to find out the influence of self-compassion on employees’ performance in an educational institute.

Literature Review

2.1 Self-Compassion and Performance

Compassion is a basis of employee satisfaction that may divert employee’s attention from task accomplishment or may increase ones performance (Vieker, 2018). This probability stimulated

this study to test the impact of self-compassion on employees' performance at the workplace. Previous literature determines the relationship between self-compassion and employees' performance (Reizer, 2019; Hur, Moon & Rhee, 2016; Eldin, 2017; Vieker, 2018). The effects of self-compassion on employees' performance have been tested by Yarnell and Neff (2012). They found a 22% variance in employee performance caused by self-compassion.

There is a positive link between self-compassion and job satisfaction (Abaci & Arda, 2013), while, job satisfaction is defined as, "positive attitude towards work increases job satisfaction which in return enhances the performance of the individual" (Susanty & Miradipta, 2013). Akin (2014) conducted a study in Egypt to find a direct link between self-compassion and employees' performance. The author revealed a positive link between self-compassion and the performance of the employees. Hur, Moon, and Rhee (2016) also showed a positive association between self-compassion and employee job performance. Similarly, compassionate behavior has a direct effect on the performance of employees at the workplace (Eldin, 2017).

"Self-compassion enhances performance as it reduces the negative emotions" (Neff & Knox, 2017). Vieker (2018) found self-compassion caused a 30% variance in proactivity. Recently, Reizer (2019) found that self-compassion linked positively to employee's job performance. Research also concluded that self-compassion may also encourage prosocial behaviors at workplace (Reizer, 2019), while prosocial behavior leads to increase employee performance (Baruch et al., 2004). On the bases of previous studies, it can be hypothesized:

H1: There is a positive link between self-compassion and employees' performance

2.2 Self-Compassion and Psychological Functioning

Psychological functioning is the state of mind and consisted of many other manifest variables. These manifest variables are positive and negative behavioral elements. It has been found that self-compassion, having positive characteristics in nature, is positively associated with positive behaviors (Neff et al., 2004; Boehm & Lyubomirsky, 2008; Barnard & Curry, 2011; Seligman, 2012). Neff and colleagues (2007b) explored the relationship between self-compassion and the positive components of the psychological state of mind. They found that self-compassion correlates positively with: the promoting happiness, individual initiative, optimism, happiness, well-being, and mental health.

Previously the relationship between self-compassion and psychological functioning was examined by Gilbert and Proctor (2007), they concluded from their results that, self-

compassion caused significant variance in positive functioning. These results also consistent with previous findings of Neff (2003b), as she reported that self-compassion can predict mental health and psychological well-being. According to the previous literature, “self-compassion considered as a positive psychological strength and a source of happiness” (Reizer, 2019). A great deal of research shows that self-compassion linked positively with happiness (Abaci & Arda, 2013; Diener & Lucas, 2000) curiosity and exploration (Diener & Lucas, 2000) personal growth and initiative (Berlyne, 1966) positive affect (Abaci & Arda, 2013; Neff et al., 2007) and optimism (Abaci & Arda, 2013; Neff et al., 2007; Breen et al., 2010). So, it can be hypothesized that:

H2: There is a positive link between self-compassion and psychological functioning

2.3 Psychological Functioning and Employee’s performance

Choudhary et al. (2017) stated that, “employees’ performance is a combination of task performance (technical competence of the task) and contextual performance (based on employee’s positive behavior and attitude to develop a productive environment in which the main task can be performed)”. Previous research shows a link between positive psychological functioning and performance as; happiness was tested with employees’ performance and concluded that both happiness and performance with collaboration make an organization successful (Awada, Johar & Ismail, 2019; Fisher, 2003). While, optimism is also a positive psychological construct (Saligman, 1998), a higher level of performance is linked with a higher level of optimism (Saligman & Schulman, 1986).

The association between the psychological component (mental health) and employee performance examined by Usman, (2017), who found that higher positive psychological functioning is beneficial for the increased employees’ job performance at the workplace. Deci et al., (2011) suggested by their findings that, exposure to positive psychological practices (including happiness, curiosity, and exploration, personal growth, and initiatives, positive affect, and optimism) increases positive outcomes, which lead to enhanced performance. In addition, positive psychological practices create a charged behavior of positive influence that produces happy, creative, active, and determinant behavior (Geue, 2017) which also increases performance (Tsai, Chen & Liu, 2007; Barsade, 2002). So it can be hypothesized that:

H3: There is a positive relationship between psychological functioning and employee performance

2.4 Psychological functioning as Mediator in the Relationship between Self-compassion and Employee's performance

Compassionate behavior has a direct effect on the employees performance at the workplace (Eldin, 2017). The relationship between compassion and employees' job performance was also tested by Hur, Moon, and Rhee (2016) and their study showed a positive link between self-compassion and employee job performance. The positive association between self-compassion and employee performance was also found by Akin and Akin (2015).

In addition, prior research also linked the self-compassion with psychological characteristics such as wellbeing (Gilbert & Proctor, 2007), they documented that self-compassion was a predictor of enhanced psychological health and caused significant variance in positive psychological functioning. Self-compassion has also been associated to curiosity, emotional intelligence, and intellectual flexibility (Martin, Stagers & Anderson, 2011; Heffernan, Griffin, McNulty & Fitzpatrick, 2010; Neff et al., 2008). People who experienced greater self-compassion reported greater psychological well-being (Akin, 2008a).

Likewise, psychological functioning has been investigated with employees' performance. In order to measure the relationship of psychological functioning with employees' performance, it was found that positive psychological determinants including; happiness (Natasha, & Francisco, 2016; Fisher 2010; Lyubomirsky et al., 2005), curiosity, and exploration (Leherissey, 1971; Mussel, 2013; Hakshaw, 2018), personal growth and initiative (Yakunina, Weigold & Weigold, 2013) linked with employees' performance. Prior studies also demonstrated that there is a association between positive affectivity and performance (Staw & Barsade, 1993). Pressman and Cohen (2005) also revealed that positive affect is a strongly influence the performance.

These link between self-compassion and performance, self-compassion, and positive psychological functioning and between positive psychological functioning and performance indicate the mediating role of positive psychological functioning in these relationships. In this regard, the mediating role of psychological functioning is missing in the relationship between self-compassion and employees' performance in the previous literature. So, it can be hypothesized that:

H4: Psychological functioning mediates in the relationship between self-compassion and employees' performance.

It is examined theoretically that, self-compassion has been researched in organizational psychology, the compassion is described commonly as a feeling condition (Dutton et al., 2014), while, cognitive theory of human behavior best explains this relationship of self-compassion and employees' performance which was presented by Skinner (1953). According to this theory, the potential benefits of real human behavior become so valuable to organizational success. This theory stated that the performance of an individual depends upon his behavior and cognition process (mental process).

Figure 1: Hypothesized Model

2.4 Theoretical Support

This study is based on three psychological theories of the organization: the self-regulation or self-control theory, the self-determination theory, and the PEMRA model of performance. The regulation theory describes how psychological processes transform into action. Self-regulation theory is dependent on the psychological notion of self-regulation and control (Akerman, 2018). The self-regulation is control over oneself, which relates to the ability of an individual to do what is perceived as right instead of complying with every passing urge and instinct. This theory holds that humans are active agents in their own way rather than passive recipients of external stimuli. Research has shown that self-regulation improves performance.

The self-determination theory, which concentrated on resources focuses on how a person interacts with and depends on others. According to self-determination theory, motivation and wellbeing are fuelled by meeting the fundamental needs for autonomy, competence, and connection. According to self-determination theory, human development is driven by three fundamental psychological needs: relatedness, competence, and autonomy. Deci and Ryan (2000) mentioned that, autonomy is the sense of having a choice and voluntarily supporting one's actions. People have a psychological desire to feel competent, according to research.

Seligman (2012) established the PERMA Model by identifying five elements that individuals seek because they are inherently motivating and enhance wellbeing. The five dimensions of the PERMA Model of performance and engagement Meaning, Relationships, Positive Emotion, Accomplishment, and Engagement combine to create a higher order construct that forecasts the success of communities, organisations, groups, and countries, according to positive psychology (Forgeard et al., 2011). The components are defined and quantified separately from one another and are sought after for their own reason (Seligman, 2012).

Each of the PERMA components has been found to be significantly positively correlated with physical health, vitality, work satisfaction, life satisfaction, and commitment within organisations (Kern, Waters, Alder, & White, 2014). The PERMA model considerably influences performance, according to earlier research. Furthermore, according to Seligman (2011) and Judge et al. (2001), this approach enhances organisational competitiveness in addition to highlighting the need of establishing a good and meaningful work environment to support employee performance.

Methodology

This research applied interpretivism research philosophy, quantitative research design and deductive approach (testing the hypotheses developed from previous literature) to analyze the association among the variables: self-compassion, psychological functioning, and employees' performance.

3.1 Sample and Population

The target population for the current study was the teaching faculty of higher education institutes in Balochistan, Pakistan. The selected population is justified for the current research as teaching faculty is high concern and responsible for compassionate behaviour. Teaching faculty directly engage with the management and students with practical realities due to unique nature of job the selected population are well trained, specialized and diverse expertise towards their job. However, the data of all the faculty members of universities in Balochistan was not available online and the population was not well defined so, this study used non-probability sampling (as suggested by Saunders et al., 2009), and convenience sampling strategy for the given population (based on budget and time circumstances). According to Green (1991), a sample size of at least five participants per variable for analytical methods is required. This study collected data from 382 respondents.

3.2 Measures

The cross-sectional timeframe was used to collect the data and the questionnaire (consist of four sections) was used as an instrument for data collection for relevant study variables. According to Saunders, Thornhill, and Lewis (2003), the questionnaire is the most widely used

tool for data collection. This study employed a self-compassion scale created by Neff (2003b) consists of 12 items e.g. “I try to be loving towards myself when I’m feeling emotional pain”, employees’ performance scale developed by Brockner et al., (1992) and adapted by May et al. (2002), Kuvaas (2006) and Şahin (2010) was used. The sample item included was “I almost always perform better than what can be characterized as acceptable performance”.

Psychological functioning measures included: Lyubomirsky and Lepper, (1999), Happiness scale with sample item such as “Some people are generally very happy. They enjoy life regardless of what is going on, getting the most out of everything. To what extent does this characterization describe you?” Kashdan, Rose, and Fincham (2004), Curiosity and exploration scale was used. The sample item was like “I would describe myself as someone who actively seeks as much information as I can in a new situation”. For measuring Personal growth initiative, the scale of Robitschek (1998) including the item “I have a good sense of where I am headed in my life” was used. Positive affect scale by Bradburn and Caplovitz, 1965; Bradburn, (1969) was adopted to measure the “activeness, determined, attentiveness”. Optimism scale by Scheier & Carver (1985) was adopted with sample item “in uncertain times, I usually expect the best”.

3.3 Procedure

This study used the survey method as it is a useful approach to analyze large samples (Konting, 1990). Measurement items were administered to the sample of 450 teaching faculty of universities through hard questionnaires and online links to the six universities of Balochistan. Both male and female teachers were accessed.

In this research, to find the association between self-compassion, psychological functioning, and employees’ performance: Pearson correlation coefficient, while, to analyze the model: structural equation modeling was utilized. For descriptive and inferential statistics; SPSS software (26 version) and Smart PLS.3 were used.

Results

Results of the demographic analysis showed that the sample (382) was comprised of both male (60.5%) and female (39.5%) participants. From 25 to 30 years of age, the frequency of the respondents was 117 (30.6). The majority of the participants (32.5%) were between 31 and 35 years of age, From 36 to 40 the sample size was 81 (21.2%) and from 41 to 45 years the respondents' frequency was 54 (14.1%) and 1.6% respondents were from the age of 46 to 50.

4.1 Preliminary data analysis (Descriptive statistics)

The descriptive statistics were tested for all scale scores by using computed variables of the scale and also by each item (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988; Kline, 2005). Authors (Bentler & Chou, 1987) stated that every construct must have three items to measure the standard CFA, and the loaded value must be greater than 0.40 of each factor (Hair et al., 1998). However, for high strength of correlation between items, the value must be less than 0.85 (Kline, 2005).

The results of the factor loading (factor loading shows the reliability of each construct with its items) demonstrated value greater than 0.40. According to the results, CFA revealed that the items used to measure self-compassion loaded on a single factor. Accordingly, a composite measure of employee performance (EP) was computed by six items that were loaded on a single factor. Psychological functioning was measured by its five positive dimensions and each dimension showed the loading value greater than .40 as mentioned by Hair et al., (1998) and loaded on a single scale. All scales demonstrated acceptable estimates.

4.2 Reliability Test (Cronbach Alpha)

Reliability was assessed by the internal consistency of the questionnaire reporting the Cronbach alpha coefficient. Results showed the internal consistency measured by Cronbach’s alpha is sufficiently reliable. The internal consistency coefficients of three subscales were 0.78, .76, and .73 respectively (as shown below in table 4.1).

4.3 Correlation analysis of the constructs.

A Pearson correlation coefficient was used to measure the relationship between the variables. Correlations coefficients between self-compassion (SC) scores, employee performance (EP) scores, dimensions of psychological functioning, and internal reliability.

Table 4.1 Measurement Model Evaluation

	TSC	EP	HP	CE	PGI	PA	OP
Total Self-compassion				(.51)			
Self-rated performance				.44**	(.52)		
Happiness		.47**	.43**	(.40)			

Curiosity and exploration	.41**	0.38	.31**	(.54)
Personal growth initiative	.35*	.57**	.18**	.32** (.44)
Positive affect	0.51	0.39	0.24	0.32 .29** (.54)
Optimism	0.47	.28**	.29**	0.18 .16* .23** (.47)

Note: Bold entries indicate the square root of AVE, off-diagonal values indicate the correlations among variables.

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

N=382

As preliminary evidence of correlation coefficients between the factors (i.e., the correlations between self-compassion and employee performance is positive (.44) and positively related to the positive psychological function; happiness, curiosity, and exploration, personal growth initiative and optimism (.47, .41, .35, 0.51 and .47) respectively. A positive and significant relationship has been found between employee performance and five dimensions of psychological functioning as mentioned in table 4.1.

4.4 Hypothesis Results

4.4.1 Self-compassion and employee performance

Results showed that 19% ($R^2=.19$) variance was explained by self-compassion in employee performance. While the beta coefficient showed a positive and significant relationship between them ($b=.303$, $p=.000b$). The results indicated that a rise in self-compassion would lead to higher employee performance, supporting the main effect hypothesis.

4.4.2 Self-compassion and psychological functioning

The relationship between self-compassion and positive psychological functioning (Curiosity and exploration, happiness, personal growth and initiative, positive affect and optimism) have been tested and results showed positive link of self-compassion with happiness ($R^2= .219$, $b= .258$, $p= .000b$), Curiosity and exploration ($R^2= .20$, $b= .148$, $p= .005b$), personal growth and initiative ($R^2= .14$, $b=.173$, $p= .019b$). While more, the results of self-compassion and positive affect showed that the positive relationship between these two variables exists ($b=.052$, $p=$

.991). Self-compassion and optimism results demonstrated that there is positive associated between these two constructs ($R^2 = .110$) and this relationship is statistically significant ($p = .002b$). The regression coefficient between the self-compassion and optimism is positive ($b = .08$).

4.4.3 Positive psychological functioning and Employees' Performance

Results showed that happiness is positively and significantly linked with employees' performance ($b = .543$, $p = .000b$), curiosity and exploration linked positively and statistically significant ($b = .018$, $p = .014$), personal growth and initiative is linked positively and significantly ($b = .130$, $p = .000b$), positive affect positively and significant ($b = .089$, $p = .045b$), and optimism positively and statistically significantly linked with employee performance ($b = 0.29$, $p = .001$).

4.4.4 Mediating effect of Psychological Functioning between SC and EP

To find the impact of psychological functioning as a mediator between the association of self-compassion and employee performance, the Process Macro test was applied. The results showed that there exists a positive and statistically significant relation between self-compassion and happiness ($b = .2579$, $p = .000$). Self-compassion and CE showed a positive and significant relationship ($b = .1484$, $p = .005$). The link between self-compassion and PGI was positive and significant ($b = .1730$, $p = .019$). Self-compassion was having relation with positive affect ($b = .0004$, $p = .991$) and positive and non-significant relationship with optimism ($b = -.0077$, $p = .719$).

After the results of X to M, the results of mediating variables and employee performance (M to Y) demonstrated that happiness ($b = .3202$, $p = .000$), Curiosity and Exploration positively ($b = 0.1278$, $p = .000$), PGI positively ($b = .1207$, $p = .000$), positive affect positively ($b = .0469$, $p = .266$) and optimism also positively linked with employee performance ($b = .251$, $p = .001$). The relationship between self-compassion to employee performance (X to Y) was positive and significant ($b = .216$, $p = .000$). The direct effect of self-compassion to employee performance was $.2161$, ($p = .000$) and the total effect was $b = .302$, $p = .000$).

Indirect effect(s) of X on Y: showed that total indirect effect is $.0865$ and with each mediating variable as mentioned: Happiness $.0826$, CE: $-.0190$, PGI: $.0209$, Positive affect: $.000$ and Optimism: $.0019$ respectively, with a level of confidence 95% and 5000 bootstrap samples for percentile bootstrap confidence intervals.

These results confirmed that there is a partial mediating effect between self-compassion and employees' performance by following Preacher and Hayes's (2008). Additionally, the indirect effect results were taken as evidence for mediation which was statistically significant (t -value > 1.96 , $p < 0.05$) (as mentioned by; Preacher & Hayes, 2004 and cited by Zhao et al., 2010).

Discussion

The current study was conducted to find out the association between self-compassion with employees' performance and the mediating role of psychological functioning in the association between self-compassion and employees' performance. According to our knowledge, no study has been conducted to consider the mediating role of psychological functioning in the link. So, the findings of the current study add to the contemporary literature by emphasizing such a mechanism.

The results of the study showed that self-compassion and employee performance were linked positively. According to these findings, employees with more self-compassionate behavior reported high job performance at the workplace. These findings also supported by prior studies (Boellinghaus, Jones & Hutton, 2012; Landgraf, 2013). Boellinghaus et al. (2012) suggested that sympathetic behavior leads to high job performance.

The relationship between self-compassion and positive psychological functioning has been analyzed with its five positive dimensions (happiness, curiosity and exploration, personal growth and initiative, positive affect, and optimism).

The association between self-compassion and happiness was positive and suggested that kind and caring people are happier than others (Diener & Lucas, 2000). Secondly, the positive link between self-compassion and curiosity showed that self-compassion increases excited response to prevailing knowledge, seeking new information to solve a problem by a systematic approach (observation, consultation, and directed thinking). Previous literature also shows that employees who are kind and caring and having common humanity always seek new knowledge and problem-solving behavior (Berlyne, 1966).

The results of the study found a positive association between self-compassion and personal growth. It means that an increase in self-compassion will also cause an increase in personal

growth and initiative. These results demonstrated that self-compassionate people have skills that help them to grow personally (Robitschek, 2003). It is also argued by scholars that people with self-compassion characteristics have a unique contribution to the world and balanced life (Karademas, 2006).

The results also indicated that self-compassion has positive relationship with positive affect. According to these results, self-compassionate people are kind, caring towards self and determined, inspired, and attentive towards their objectives having mankind attitude. Alert and active characteristics of positive affect differentiate them as self-compassionate people (Lutz et al., 2004). Finally, it was found that there is association between self-compassion and optimism. These results suggest that self-compassionate employees are optimistic about their future. Self-compassion helps to maintain optimistic expectations about the future (Scheier et al., 1994).

Overall, these results are according to the previous study by Neff and Dahm (2014). The empirical findings of the current study have shown that self-compassion is positively linked with better psychological functioning.

The findings of the study also indicated a positive connection between positive psychological functioning and employees' performance. The impact of happiness on employees' performance was found positive which means happy employees have higher performance. It is argued by scholars that happy employees are more productive than unhappy employees (Natasha, & Francisco, 2016). Fisher (2010) and Lyubomirsky et al. (2005) also concluded happiness is related to the core and contextual performance as happy individuals are successful and success brings happiness. And those who are happy engage in behaviors that create improved outcomes in psychological, tangible, and even physiological domains.

The results of the study also have shown a positive link between curiosity and exploration with employee performance as was hypothesized. It is argued that with an increase in curiosity and exploration, the employees' performance also increases because curiosity produces a mixture of pleasant and unpleasant feelings (Leherissey, 1971; Berlyne, 1967). Hakshaw (2018) concluded in his findings that, curiosity is a key to sustainable performance. These findings are also similar with previous results of Mussel (2013), who argued about curiosity as a predictor variable for work-related outcomes and causes variance in employee performance.

A positive relationship was found between personal growth and initiative with employees' performance. These results are also supported by previous studies (Meyers et al., 2015; Yakunina, Weigold & Weigold, 2013; Robitschek, 1998) that, optimistic approach increases the employees' performance. The relationship between positive affect and employee performance was found positively linked with each other. Previous studies also demonstrated that significant relationships between positive affectivity and performance exist (Staw & Barsade, 1993). Pressman and Cohen (2005) also revealed that positive affect has a strong impact on performance.

Finally, optimism was found positively linked with employees' performance. These findings are also supported by prior studies (Betts, Morgan & Castiglia, 2008; Chhajer, Rose & Joseph, 2018). Previous studies determined that high optimism leads to higher employees' performance. Nawaz (2018) also concluded that optimism energizes employee performance. The results of the current study suggested that people with sympathetic behavior were more optimistic.

The mediating role of Psychological Functioning

Results showed that happiness, curiosity, and exploration mediate in the relationship between self-compassion and employees' performance positively. Personal growth and initiatives partially mediate in the association between self-compassion and employees' performance. Positive affect and optimism also have a positive mediating effect between these relationships. These findings are also in support of Deci et al. (2001) study. They suggested on the bases of their findings that exposure to positive psychological practices (including happiness, curiosity, and exploration, personal growth and initiatives, positive affect, and optimism) increases employees' performance. In addition, it is further documented in the literature that positive psychological practices create a charged behavior of positive influence that produces happy, creative, active, and determinant behavior in care of self as mankind, humanity, mindfulness, leading to better performance (Geue, 2017).

5.1 Implications

This study provides a new perspective to enhance employees' performance by analyzing its link with self-compassion at work. This study presents an empirical framework for the research through investigating the mediating effect of psychological functioning between the

association of self-compassion, and employee performance in teaching faculty of higher education institutions of Balochistan, Pakistan.

These findings will be beneficial for public managers and decision-makers to give importance to the effect of self-compassion in all sectors of working institutions. Firstly this study will be helpful to provide some ideas about the management of human resources and their behavior effectively and efficiently. Secondly, the mediating role of psychological functioning should enable the decision-makers to shape the organizational environment in such a way that it will be according to the comfort of every employee, so the employee will be able to perform up to the benchmark of the institution.

5.2 Limitations and future Recommendations

This study focused on overall self-compassion, while, Self-compassion has three components and the relationship of each component of self-compassion with employees' performance and psychological functioning can be measured in the future. Furthermore, psychological functioning has eleven dimensions (six positives and five negatives), so, other positive and negative dimensions of psychological functioning can also be tested by the researchers. The sample size, sampling technique, respondents' context, and timeframe are also limitations for generalization of the results of the study.

Conclusion

The current study extends earlier researches by offering primary indication for the mediating role of positive psychological functioning in the link between self-compassion and employees' performance. Findings of current research study suggest that, people who practice self-compassion also tend to have more positive states of mind in order to increase the performance towards their goals.

It is concluded from the results of the study that; self-compassion increases the performance of the employees. In other words, self-compassion, having positive characteristics (mankind, mindfulness, self-kindness, common humanity, self-care), which positively influence positive psychological functioning (which is a state of mind of an employee) including; happiness, curiosity, and exploration, personal growth, and initiative. It is also concluded that positive psychological functioning increases the employees' performance.

This study also examined the mediating effect of positive psychological functioning between self-compassion and employees' performance (by each dimension of positive psychological

functioning separately). The results showed that happiness, personal growth and initiatives, curiosity, and exploration increase the relationship of self-compassion and employee performance positively, while, positive affect has partially mediate between the relationship of self-compassion and employees' performance.

In conclusion, this research has shown that self-compassion apart from personality traits is also a learned skill (Gilbert, 2010; Gilbert & Procter, 2006). So, the findings of this study will help in promoting employee behavior by enhancing their self-compassion. Based on the findings of such a study, it can be claimed that self-compassion may result in enhanced employees' performance which in turn increases the productivity of organizations.

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